

Exploring Happiness Level of Teachers working in Private Educational Institutions in Islamabad: A Case Study of Beacon House School System

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Abstract

The purpose of research study was to explore the “happiness level of teachers” at Beaconhouse Metropolitan Campus, Islamabad. It was a study to find out the comparison of happiness with different variables on the basis of demographic characteristics. It has been concluded from research that the quality of human resource and environment of an organization depends on happy mental state and feelings of workers. It is important for schools to measure how happy mental state is responsible for quality education and learning and also how much educational institutes expects happiness among teachers. The study aims at finding out the happiness level of teachers of BMC and of developing an action plan for developing a better happy workplace. Both descriptive and referential statistics were used for data analysis. The sample study included all male and female teachers of Beaconhouse with the random sampling, sample size (n=100). The data was collected by using Oxford Questionnaire for Happiness (Hills, (2002). Data collected was analyzed using t-test, ANOVA and Chi-square. The ultimate goal of research was realization of teachers' sense of happiness, which is an inevitable requirement of meaningful education. The objective of research study was to measure happiness level of teachers working in BMC for developing teachers' motivational program and again measuring this happiness level after some interval using same tool in order to see the impact of motivational program on teacher's happiness level. The result shows general happiness score of teachers is above average which exhibit most of the teachers are happy with no significant relation between happiness level of teachers on the basis of demographic characteristics. As most of the variables of study have shown no significant relationship, therefore future study might be conducted on other variables such as impact of Parental relationship, working environment, managerial style on happiness level of teachers.

Keywords: happiness level, performance, well-being

1. Introduction

The term “happiness” is used as a synonym to “life as well as job contentment and engagement”. It might include the term organizational commitment and flow. In recent years, importance of teacher education is getting popularity with the impact of globalization.

In the contextual study of happiness in education teaching, different research studies has shown that happiness of teachers' is an indicator of students' happiness state, while degree of happiness of student figure out level of school performance and achievement (Duckworth, Quinn & Seligman, 2009). However, research proved that positive attitude of teachers and happiness results into academic achievement of students (Sutton & Wheatley, 2003). It was argued that positive emotions of teachers might affect pupils' motivation level. (Turner, Midgley, Meyer, Gheen, Anderman, Kang & Patrick, 2002). Unfortunately, various research studies show work load burden, time constraint (Chan, 1998) students' behavioral issues and strong emotional association of teachers with students develops high demands from job. Thus, creates hurdles while reaching to the state of happiness. In addition, some of external factors such as non-cooperative angry parents & non-supportive peers (Lasky, 2000) are also the hurdles in reaching at the happiness state which can ultimately result in the shape of frustration. These uncontrollable factors increase stress, anxiety, depression & low job satisfaction level (Tadić, Bakker & Oerlemans, 2013; Arshad & Ali, 2016; Sajid & Ali, 2018; Ashraf & Ali, 2018; Kassem et al., 2019; Roussel et al., 2021; Senturk & Ali, 2022). For Example, previous researches concluded that lack of flexibility in teachers' relationships with the pupil results into passiveness and de-motivation thus creates unhappy students (Van, 2004). However, teachers keep on feeling satisfaction and happiness while working (Hakanen, Bakker & Schaufeli, 2006). Literature shows that teachers feel confident and positive when their pupils make progress and show responsive behaviour (Hargreaves, 2000) such as when they meet deadlines and complete their tasks, and can get support from peers. According to theory of self-determination (Ryan, Huta & Deci, 2008) work motivation of is personalized and depends upon intrinsic motivation that helps in coping with difficult work situation. Smith and Lazarus (1993) say personalized desire to cope with high job demands varies from person to person and brings happiness as a final outcome. In the similar way, motivation level of workforce has a great influence on their efforts and energy that is invested in the task. This includes many emotions felt involved during tasks (Sheldon, Turban, Brown, Barrick & Judge, 2003).

In this way, stimuli for motivation act as a motivational factor that secures teachers and other employees from high job demands expectations & maintain various happiness scores within their working environment. It was concluded from researches that degree of happiness varies from person to person while performing diversified working activities and it also changes on different working days and time. Therefore, some of the researchers have

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focused on personalized fluctuations in teachers' happiness, motivation level and workplace demand. In short, researches have exhibited strong relationship between change in the state of happiness level and its prompt impact in specific environment context during specific time period (Kahneman, Krueger, Schkade, Schwarz & Stone, 2004). The main purpose of research study was to develop a working environment which facilitates staff happiness through collaboration with school staff, therefore, from researchers' point of view; determination of teacher's happiness level at workplace is an important factor. Being researchers, our key concern for teaching staff is to increase their motivational level. It is only possible, if we knew the factors or different aspects of their happiness. Once, we knew the factors affecting happiness level of teaching staff in private institute, we can design a program that will facilitate the happiness at work.

We have also observed the relationship between different variables like age, marital status, years in service, gender, permanent or contractual employment on the happiness level of students. The result of the study may be used to design a program to enhance the happiness level of teachers. The organization where research was conducted is observing low morale and motivational level of teachers. The administration wants to design a motivational program and wants to bring some changes in administration policies and leadership styles for improving the motivational level of teacher, and it is only possible if they knew about happiness level of teachers and the factors that are generally impacting happiness score. Therefore, the researchers have collected data for determining the happiness level of teaching staff in Beaconhouse School System in Metropolitan Campus, Girls and Boys section. This study will help in determining the happiness score and identifying the relationship in between different variables while measuring happiness level of teaching staff. The study is also conducted to identify the factors behind happiness of teachers at workplace. The research will be conducted again after implementation of new administration policies for improving motivational level of teachers. The general or main objective of the study is to determine teachers' happiness level in Middle and Secondary schools. While, the main objective was broken down into various specific objectives in order to find out relationship between different variables. The research objectives are as follows:

- To explore out the happiness level of teachers of Beaconhouse Metropolitan Campus.
- To compare the happiness score of the Female & Male teachers
- To compare the happiness level of the Regular and Contractual staff
- To compare the happiness level on the basis of years of service
- To compare the happiness level on the basis of marital status
- To find out relationship between employee pay/ salary on happiness level
- To analyze the factors behind happiness levels

1.1. Significance of Study

In recent years, mental, emotional happiness and well being of a employees has gained a lot of attention in various researches. The reason behind is the increasing impedes on the relationship between happier and satisfied employee and better labor productivity. This happiness in contextual workplace scenario is further linked up with better community relationships and citizenships. The happier an employee, the better will be the creativity and mental state of mind. The better is the creativity; the more challenging will be the organizational environment. Many researchers have proved that happy people perform better (Seligman, Ernst, Gillham, Reivich & Linkins, 2009). So, we can conclude that happy teachers produce outstanding students who can perform better in any professional regardless of the fact that how stressful a job is. That means happy and satisfied workers creates conducive and challenging environment. The better is the cognitive and psychological state of employee, the better will be the performance and this in turn produces better citizens and better nation. In a country with happier citizens with better cognitive health and good emotional satisfaction, overall productivity and creativity of nation improves. Therefore, it is very important to measure the degree of happiness of teachers. The happier a teacher is, the better will be the teacher-student relationship. This good relationship helps in creating happy students and happy students results into better academic achievement (Huebner & Alderman, 1993). The importance of conducting this research in Beaconhouse School System is to assess the happiness level of teachers and to identify the factors leading to happiness. These factors will be used by administration and management for designing teacher motivational program.

2. Literature Review

In previous studies, most of the psychologists have focused on stress and anxiety factor of human unhappiness and completely neglected the positive perspective of human being. Happiness is a state of satisfaction and well-being. It is a cognitive process of mind which is related to satisfying and pleasurable state and experience of mind. Aristotle concluded that human beings seek happiness. Whatever goal they have in their life i.e. beauty, health, power, wealth and fame, it is valuable in their life only if they assume that these goals will make individuals happy (Csikszentmihalyi & Csikszentmihalyi, 1990).

However, in scientific term, happiness is quite a vague and non technical term as it is not measurable in true sense. Adler & Seligman (2016) has decomposed the term happiness into five scientifically measurable areas. These are engaged life means positive engagement, meaning means meaningful life, emotion means pleasant life, positive accomplishment and relationship. So, "teachers' happiness" in the education system will be defined as the teacher

working with optimism, following ethical values and have full faith in the system which is based on many external factors which results into a kind of joy which is produced by the work required to exceed and meet the expected goals. According to Seligman et.al (2009), happiness has two qualitatively aspects: one is on the basis of experienced which is also called as episodic and other is overall happiness which means trait-level. Now what is trait-level happiness? It refers to self perception of people about their life and it depends on how they generally evaluate their lives—it means evaluation of the overall quality of life favourably. But again that depends upon personal biases.

Happiness at work is a crucial indicator of job satisfaction. For example, overall happiness at work has shown significant relationship between job contentment and performance (Crede, Chernyshenko, Stark, Dalal & Bashshur, 2007) and negative relationship with fatigue and stress (Iverson, Olekalns & Erwin, , 1998) and high turnover of staff (Van Katwyk, Fox, Spector & Kelloway, 2000). Moreover, the experienced or episodic aspect of happiness has expressed positive relationship with longer-term happiness, both at domestic and professional life. Peterson, Ruch, Beermann, Park & Seligman (2007) in their research study conducted in Switzerland & UK has identified key attributes associated with life satisfaction & happiness level. These were desire, love, interest in inquiry, and determination. Among them determination is strongly related to high satisfaction level of life. All of these attributes are purely associated with meaningful and joyful life. However, It has been argued that strong personal and community relationships are strong predictors rather indicators of happiness (Argyle & Lu, 1990). Community relationships including marriage and particularly friendships have consistently direct relationship with happiness (Duckworth, Quinn & Seligman, 2009). In addition, meaningful work, including volunteering, for the cause has also shown a positive impact on happiness (Beddington, Cooper, Field, Goswami, Huppert, Jenkins, & Thomas, 2008).

2.1. Consequences of Happiness

Happiness has a positive effect on quality of life. It also lays positive impact on multiple domains such as marital life, income level, professional growth, health and friendship. So it is a main determinant of people's success in life (Diener, Lucas & Scollon, 2009). Moreover, (Hargreaves, 2000) explored the association between recurring positive emotion and specific actions. She argued that positive emotions build life-long habits and actions. These could be personal, psychological and social resources. The key attributes may include optimism, confidence, likability, energy, sociability & energized behaviour; immunity, good social behaviour, physical happiness; coping with stress and challenge; and flexibility (Demir & Weitekamp, 2007)

Summing up discussion, positive emotions have a positive relationship with creativity. However, satisfaction with life & subjective well-being has positive correlation with long-life (Danner, Snowdon & Friesen, 2001). Additionally, the consequences of happiness have been generally associated with health and positive affect of health is significantly associated with lower risk of mortality in people with diabetes. This means consequences of happiness shows impact on both psychological and physical health and wellbeing of an individual (Argyle & Lu, 1990).

2.2. Role of Human Needs Theory-In the Context of Happiness

Maslow (1943) presented a famous theory of human needs. According to him, human being satisfy their needs in a hierarchical order starting from basic physical needs, to safety needs, love and belongingness to self-esteem needs and finally the need for self-actualization. Maslow proposed these needs vary from person to person. However, in most cases though people get happiness after satisfying needs at each and every level however true happiness can only be achieved if human beings achieve higher order needs such as self esteem and self-actualization. While Maslow's theory is widely accepted and cited in various literatures (Koltko-Rivera, 2006) and is much relevant in the context of true happiness at work, however, it has received a lot of criticism (Neher, 1991). In contrast, Self Determination Theory is more valuable as it not only addresses motivation from two perspectives i.e. how behaviour is stimulated but also how behaviour is directed i.e. needs are innate rather than learned motives. Needs are more likely to be at psychological rather than physiological level. The determination of these needs is important for creating happiness at workplace.

2.3. Private Schools System in Pakistan

The Private schooling system in Pakistan has gained momentum with the impact of globalization on educational policy of a country. As International development forums are much concerned on the implication of effective education policy, better service delivery & sustainable development, therefore demand for private school education is increasing day by day. Moreover, Public schools are not able to deliver quality education due to lack of infrastructure and resources. Private school system in Pakistan has its roots in pre-independence period. In the early years after independence, most of the schools in Pakistan remained under the umbrella of religious & secular (non-governmental) organizations. That attracted mainly to high-income group in major cities. This was an era of private schools in 1990s, resulted into structural educational transformation in the school system. The main theme of private school in Pakistan is profit maximization, mostly fee based, secular and autonomous with no direct government support. However, due to deliverance of quality education by private institutes, the demand for education is increasing. Most of the private institutions are affordable and within the reach of large number of households.

2.4. Beaconhouse School System

The Beaconhouse group is operating in eight different countries and has almost 308,000 fulltime students. It is one of the largest school networks and established in November 1975 with the name of “Les Anges Montessori Academy” with nineteen toddlers, Since then, Beaconhouse has expanded into network of private schools both nationally and internationally. The main purpose is delivering meaningful and differential learning to pupils through its strategic partnership with Gymboree to post-graduation, through Beaconhouse National University and Concordia Colleges (Beaconhouse School Manual)

The Beaconhouse operates in multiple countries including Malaysia, UK, Thailand, Oman, Philippines, UAE, Belgium and Pakistan and caters to the education needs of a diverse group of individuals with different demographics and socioeconomic backgrounds. Beaconhouse is playing a leading role in diminishing the quality gap between private and public education sectors. It has further recognized the contribution of BSS internationally. As BSS is offering professional expertise to other institutes and government entities so it is becoming more competitive internationally. The mission statement of Beaconhouse is to provide quality education of an International standard through quality training, quality education & quality teaching with the focus to bring macro benefits to students, community and world. Beaconhouse gives a lot of value to its inherited heritage with special focus to meet differential needs of students. Beaconhouse is very much adapted to dynamic changes. It is very much adaptable to latest trends and innovation and is exceeding the expectations of community. BSS is equipped with modern technology with a special focus on ethical and moral values. BSS makes better and happy citizens through incorporating its learner profile attributes in students.

3. Research Methodology

3.1. Research Design

This was an action research for measuring the happiness level of teachers. For assessing the happiness level, Beaconhouse Metropolitan Campus, Islamabad Region is taken as case study.

3.2. Selection of Sample

The population of the study comprised of all the teachers (Regular and contractual), married and Unmarried, visiting and permanent of all the Secondary school Beaconhouse Schools were included. There are total 320 Teacher staff in Secondary School Campuses of Beaconhouse in Islamabad Region. The sample of one hundred (100) teachers was selected on random basis depending upon their willingness to participate in the research.

3.3. Research Instrument

The second stage of methodology is related to the formation of Questionnaire to obtain necessary particulars pertaining to the study. The data had been collected through questionnaire and analyzed by constructing tables and diagrams. The whole data was collected by Oxford Happiness Questionnaire tool which was developed by Michael Argyle & Peter Hills of Oxford Brookes University. It was originally published in 2002 in Journal of Personality & Individual Differences. It is a 29-item Oxford Happiness Questionnaire (OHQ) which is widely-used scale for measuring personal happiness. This questionnaire has 12 negatively worded items that require reverse coding before calculating the total happiness score, which is a sum of individual item scores. E.g. positively worded items include ‘I am very happy’ and negatively worded items ‘I rarely wake up feeling rested’.

3.4. Reliability and Validity of Oxford Happiness Questionnaire

According to Hills and Argyle (2002), the OHQ is supposed to measure personal happiness as a broader uni-dimensional construct and has good internal consistency, with Cronbach’s alpha at the level of 0.90 and above. Cronbach’s Alpha shows the reliability of Oxford Happiness Questionnaire. The Oxford Happiness Questionnaire is close ended questionnaire and based on Likert-scale. The Oxford Happiness Questionnaire is an instrument for measuring happiness variables. OHQ made in a Likert Scale format with five alternative answers, starting from very agree (score 5) to strongly disagree (score 1). The data demonstrated here good internal reliability and consistency ($\alpha = .92$).

4. Analysis and Interpretation of Data

“Oxford Happiness Scale” is used to collect data (Hills and Argyle, 2002) which has 29 items and participants provided feedback on each item. It was based on a Likert scale 1 to 6 (1- strongly disagree; 6-strongly agree). For statistical analysis of data, f-test, One-Way ANOVA, Independent Samples T-test and Ki-square were used.

4.1. General Happiness Level of the Secondary School Teachers of Beaconhouse School System Islamabad Region

The "Oxford Happiness Scale", a set of 29 items designed so that 18 of the 29 items are considered positive and 11 of them are considered negative. The overall average happiness score is 4.15, which is higher than average and according to OHQ, they are "quite happy". According to the Happiness Scale, high scores from positive items indicate high levels of happiness, while high scores from negative goals indicate high levels of dissatisfaction. The following Tables 1 and 2 clearly show the teacher's scores with a sample of 100, obtained from the positive and negative items, respectively. In both tables, scores are ranked in a specific ranking order, from highest score to lowest score. Table 1 shows that teachers received a score of 3.87 or higher, well above the average for the positive items.

Table -1: Mean Score of Teachers (positive items)

Positive statements	Mean	SD
Feeling able to take responsibility	4.69	1.17
Life is beautiful	4.67	1.14
I notice beauty around me	4.67	1.15
Being interested in what they do and devoting themselves	4.65	1.15
Being very interested in other people	4.37	1.87
Usually I have a positive effect on events	4.55	1.02
I am usually cheerful and happy	4.21	1.10
I always have a cheerful effect on other people	4.07	1.12
I feel quite energetic	4.06	1.22
Mentally I feel completely fit	4.05	1.28
I am very smiling	4.04	1.71
I am very happy	3.96	1.18
I have very warm feeling against almost everyone	3.87	1.25
I am quite happy with everything in my life	5.79	1.24
I find many things fun	5.56	1.23
I can save time for everything I want to do	3.57	1.25
I think life is quite rewarding	5.56	1.59
I wake up as fully rest in my morning	5.52	1.44

The tables exhibit happiness score of teachers is above average. There are five top things that are making Teachers happy, “life Is beautiful”, “They notice beauty around them”, “Being interested in what they do and devoting themselves”, “Take interest in what other people do”.

Table 2: Means Scores of Teacher (negative items)

Negative statements	Mean	SD
There is a big difference what I see and what I want to	3.02	1.40
I have trouble deciding any subject	2.88	1.41
I am very optimistic about my future	2.85	1.62
I feel like I cannot control my life	2.82	1.41
I don't think the world is a good place	2.64	1.55
I donot think I am atractive	2.33	1.26
I don't feel very healthy	2.31	1.26
I donto have very happy memories about my past	2.20	1.35
I don't enjoy being with other people	1.96	1.18
I am not happy withmyself	1.79	1.31
My life doesnot have a certain purpose and meaning	1.74	1.45

Table 2, teachers received low average points with the highest score 3.02. These tables' shows below average unhappiness score of teachers. The top 5 things that create unhappiness are as follows; “There is a huge difference between what they really do & what they wanted to do”, “They feel difficulty in deciding which subjects to select”, “They are pessimistic about their future”, “They have no control on their lives”, “They think and feel that the world is a better place”. Regarding people opinion about meaning and purpose of life, average score is 1.74 Which is very, shows the unhappiness situation of teachers.

4.2. Comparison of Happiness of teachers on the basis of Gender

Hypothesis: There is no significant difference between Female and Male Secondary school teachers of Beaconhouse Metropolitan Campus, Islamabad as far as their happiness are concerned

Table 3: Difference in Happiness Based on Gender

	Gender	N	M	t	p
Happiness	Female	67	4.32	-1.44	0.413
	Male	33	4.22		

According to statistical results, there is no statistical significance between happiness level on the basis of gender AS (t-test value = -1.44; $p > 0.05$) while $p=0.413 > 0.05$, so we accept null hypothesis.

4.3. Comparison of Happiness of Teachers on the basis of seniority

Hypothesis: There is no significant difference between happiness level of Senior and newly hired teachers.

Table 4: Difference in Happiness Based on Seniority

	Seniority/No of years	N	M	SS	f	p
Happiness	0-5 years	59	4.27	0.653	0.672	0.643
	5-10	20	4.27	0.63		
	10-15	10	4.28	0.61		
	15-20	10	4.21	0.66		

Seniority of teachers is categorized in 6 different groups ranging from (0-5, 5-10, 10-15, 15-20, 20-25). There are different teachers in each age group, average happiness scores is compared through one-way ANOVA. According to results, there is no significant relationship between happiness scores of teachers in different seniority groups as ($p=0.643>0.05$).

4.4. Comparison of Happiness of Teachers on the basis of Marital Status

Hypothesis: There is no significant difference between happiness level of married and unmarried teachers

Table 5: Differences in Happiness Based on Marital Status

	Marital Status	N	M	Chi-Square	p
Happiness	Single	25	220.55	2.044	0.360
	Married	65	226.43		
	Divorced/	06	105.66		
	Widowed	04	102.33		

Teachers were categorized in 4 different groups including (single, married, divorced and widowed). The happiness scores of each marital status groups were compared with Kruskal-Wallis test which is an alternative of ANOVA. This method is selected because of the unbalanced distribution of no. of participants in each group. According to the results, there is no statistical difference between average scores (Ki- Square = 2,043; $p > 0.05$) means there is no significant relationship between happiness score and marital status. Table 5 shows ($p=0.360>0.05$)

4.5. Comparison of Happiness of Teachers on the basis of Income

Hypothesis: There is no significant relationship of salary/pay structure on happiness level of teachers

Table 6: Happiness Level of teachers on the basis of Income

	Income	N	M	t	SD	p
Happiness	25000-35000	40	4.68	0.406	0.438	0.691
	35000-45000	45	4.96			
	45000-55000	10	4.30			
	55000-65000	05	4.25			

Teachers were categorized in 4 distinct groups on the basis of Income Level. The happiness scores of 4 groups were measured using independent t-test. According to results, there is no significant difference in happiness scores of teachers on the basis of income level ($t = 0.406$; $p > 0.05$) as ($p=0.691>0.05$)

4.6. Comparison of Happiness of Teachers on the basis of Type of Employment (Permanent or Contract)

Keeping in view the type of employees (permanent or contract), (Ki-square value was 2.043, $p>0.05$), that shows there is no statistical significant difference between permanent or contractual employees happiness level. ($p=0.365>0.05$)

Table 7: Happiness Score of teachers on the basis of type of employment

	Type of employment	N	Average order	Chi-Square	SD	p
Happiness	Permanent	80	219.55	2.043	2	0.365
	Contract	20	225.03			

5. Discussion and Conclusions

The happiness scores of Beaconhouse Metropolitan teachers were generally above average. In other words, teachers are generally happy. Highest happiness score came from "the teachers' sense of feeling responsibility while given any task in institute" that means happiness level of teachers can be raised through delegation of authority with responsibility. This research finding correlates with "Self determination theory". Research study determined one more very important factor that is contributing in higher level of happiness score and that is "Teachers' own thinking and perception about life is beautiful" and noticing beautiful environment around them. Now in researchers' opinion, this is a personal trait and varies from person to person. This is personal perception about Quality of Life. Moreover, it is intrinsic motivation that creates sense of responsibility and increases

happiness level. The lowest score that a teacher has got in positively worded items of happiness questionnaire was perception of wake up every morning with fully rested. Means most of the employees of Beaconhouse Metropolitan campus feel lethargic and lazy after getting sleep. Another factor that score relatively low in positive items is perception of employees as “Life is rewarding” means there is a room for further research over here as what are the factors that assess life as not rewarding. Now this is the general perception of teachers in BMC that life is not as they are expecting. As far as type of employment is concerned, there is no significant relationship or difference between the happiness level of permanent and contractual teachers. Hence, there is no significant relationship between teachers’ happiness and the demographic characteristics. This research is important for the happiness of the students and the contribution of happiness of the teachers.

5.1. Recommendations

This research was conducted with the purpose of determining Happiness level of teachers in Beaconhouse Metropolitan campus and the results are generalized. The significant relationship between happiness level of teachers and different demographic and other variables were determined. However, researchers are of the opinion that result may differ if we extend the research study in different school environment including private and public sectors and then comparing the happiness score of public with private schools in Pakistan. Moreover, research study can also be conducted on determining the impact of happiness levels of teachers on Job satisfaction level. As most of the variables of study has shown no significant relationship, therefore future study might be conducted on other variables such as impact of Parental relationship, working environment, managerial style on happiness level of teachers. The researchers also suggest that if Beaconhouse Metropolitan Campus wants to increase the average happiness score of teachers, they have to conduct study on exploring the impact of management style and school working environment on happiness level of teachers. As most of the teachers has shown their highest level of happiness when they will be given a specific responsibility, means management of BMC has to focus on delegation of task with responsibility. There is a need to change the management style of administration to some extent. There is a room for further research as which management style (autocratic, democratic or Laissez-Faire) is best suitable in BMC. Moreover, as teachers show low happiness score on the perception of “Life as rewarding” means more research can be conducted on which factors bring more reward to life. Generally, teachers of Beaconhouse think life is not as expected and they are not getting full reward for whatever they are working. It is recommended for BMC to design an effective motivational plan that could improve further the happiness and job satisfaction level of teachers at work.

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